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Mid-term Evaluation Report

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Abstract (for public dissemination only)	This document describes the interim findings from the evaluation and impact assessment applied in the GREAT project. It builds on the evaluation framework defined in Deliverable D5.1 and presents the findings along five impact dimensions: participants, scientific, economic, and societal. At project mid-term impact traces can be found across all four dimensions based on the evidence collected in four case studies.
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List of Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
B2B	Business-to-Business
DiBL	Dilemma-based Learning Game (a product of the GREAT partner Serious Games Interactive)
DoA	Description of Action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EC	European Commission
ETEK	Cyprus Scientific and Technical Chamber
GREAT	Games Realising Effective Affective Transformation
ISCED	International Standard Classification of Education
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
NPO	Nonprofit Organisation
UKRI	United Kingdom Research & Innovation
UNDP	United Nations Development Programme
SIG	Serious Games Interactive
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
WP	Work Package

1 Executive Summary

The GREAT project aims to explore the potential of game-based approaches in fostering political and social engagement with climate change. By integrating interactive methodologies into climate discourse, the project seeks to bridge the gap between citizens and policymakers, fostering more inclusive and participatory decision-making processes. This mid-term evaluation presents findings from four case studies—UNDP Exploratory, Play2Act, Green Jobs, and Rooftop Revolution—which have tested different game formats and engagement strategies.

The evaluation framework focuses on four impact dimensions: participant, scientific, economic, and societal. Across these dimensions, evidence suggests that game-based interventions can promote climate awareness, encourage deliberative discussions, and offer new insights into public opinion on climate policies. Findings from four case studies indicate that these interactive methods can serve as innovative data collection tools, providing policymakers and researchers with real-time insights into public attitudes and engagement levels. The participant dimension further indicates that game-based discussions can improve understanding of current climate policy issues and influence beliefs about climate change, though the effectiveness of game-based discussions varies based on audience demographics, experience of the discussions, and facilitation quality. On a societal level, the project has helped engage diverse stakeholder groups, including young people, policy experts, and community leaders, by offering a structured yet flexible approach to participatory policy-making. The economic dimension has highlighted the potential for new business models in the gaming industry, particularly in developing socially responsible gaming applications and new engagement platforms.

However, challenges remain. Demographic diversity in participation has been uneven, with certain groups (e.g., younger and male participants) being overrepresented in some of the case studies. Additionally, sustaining the economic viability of these approaches beyond the project's lifespan will require strategic partnerships with the gaming industry and policy institutions.

Overall, the mid-term findings affirm that game-based participation is a scalable, engaging, and informative tool for climate action. As the project moves into its second phase, further refinement of engagement strategies, data analysis methodologies, and dissemination efforts are envisioned. The goal is to ensure long-term impact by embedding game-based approaches into policy consultation, educational outreach, and community-driven climate action.

2 Introduction

This mid-term evaluation report provides an interim assessment of the project's progress, highlighting both achievements and challenges. It synthesises findings from four case studies exploring different game-based engagement strategies:

1. UNDP Exploratory: An early-stage study investigating the feasibility of embedding climate-related surveys into commercial video games, targeting a digitally literate audience.
2. Play2Act: A large-scale follow-up study that expanded on the UNDP Exploratory case, distributing surveys across multiple game studios and reaching over 900.000 players globally.
3. Green Jobs: A study focused on engaging young people in Austria through a dilemma-based role-playing game, assessing perceptions of climate-related careers and the motivations behind career choices.
4. Rooftop Revolution: A participatory urban planning initiative in Cyprus, using a dilemma-based role-playing game to engage stakeholders in discussions about green infrastructure and rooftop greening.

The evaluation examines the project's impact through four core dimensions: participant, scientific, economic, and societal. The participant dimension assesses individual engagement and changes in climate beliefs and behaviours. The scientific dimension explores contributions to academic knowledge and methodologies. The economic dimension considers the commercial potential of game-based approaches, and the societal dimension focuses on fostering public participation and enhancing community engagement in policymaking. Combining quantitative and qualitative methods such as surveys, feedback, and network analyses, the evaluation offers insights into the effectiveness of game-based participation and its role in climate action and policymaking.

The report is structured into several key chapters. It begins with an overview of the contextual setting of the GREAT case studies, outlining their objectives, methodologies, and implementation periods. This is followed by a chapter on data, methods, and analysis, which details the quantitative and qualitative approaches used to evaluate the case studies. The core findings of the mid-term evaluation are then presented across the four dimensions of evaluation: participant, scientific, societal, and economic. The final chapter of the report consists of conclusions and outlook,

summarising key insights, reflecting on the strengths and limitations of the approaches tested, and outlining recommendations for the final phase of the project. In the Appendices, additional information, such as the detailed questionnaires applied in the case studies as well as the network graphs are provided.

3 Contextual Setting: the GREAT Case Studies

As outlined in the GREAT project DoA, our research suggested two distinct approaches when it comes to game-based interventions. We distinguish between a quiz game (PlanetPlay platform) and a dilemma game (SGI Platform) engagement strategy, where the first aims to reach a large number in terms of engagement and large quantitative data insight, while the second approach is more qualitative and interactive in nature. For this mid-term evaluation report, we rely on data collected in four distinct case studies: 2 PlanetPlay platform approaches (UNDP Exploratory and Play2Act) and 2 SGI Platform approaches (Green Jobs and Rooftop Revolution). Each case study is briefly outlined in the following. Note that there are more detailed case study reports available for each of them.

3.1 UNDP Exploratory

As indicated in the name, this case study was exploratory in nature. It ran from December 2023 till March 2024, involving the case study sponsor United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) and the GREAT project research team. The aim was to explore innovative ways to engage young, digitally literate individuals in policy discussions on the climate emergency by embedding surveys into popular commercial video games. In co-design with the case study sponsor, a set of survey questions were defined and launched via different methods in the multiplayer online battle arena game SMITE. A full description can be found in the case study report by Hollins et al. (2024)¹.

3.2 UNDP Play2Act

The second quiz game case study is a follow up from the UNDP Exploratory study and includes a large number of game studios launching the survey globally to a total of over 1 million gamers. The survey launched in September 2024 and is still ongoing at the time of writing. Together with the case study sponsor UNDP, the GREAT team re-designed the survey questions, including questions about personal motivation and sentiments regarding climate change and the potential of video games. The survey reached over 900.000 engagements and a total of over 180.000 completed

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13986359>

surveys. The Play2Act survey offered gamers the option to sign up for more engagement in case of interest on the topic of climate action. In a next step, we plan to engage those interested in open data sprints where we will engage and collectively dive deeper into the open data collected in Play2Act. As the case study is still not fully completed by the time of writing this report, we will only include partial findings from this large-scale case study.

3.3 Green Jobs

The Green Jobs case study was conducted in Austria from October 2023 till October 2024. The primary goal of this case study was to assess the effectiveness of game-based methodologies in engaging youth in discussions about climate jobs and to explore their motivations and perceptions regarding careers in the climate sector, next to the overarching GREAT research questions. The Klimafonds, an institution working directly for the Austrian Federal Ministry for Climate Action, Environment, Energy, Mobility, Innovation and Technology to address climate issues at national level, served as the case study sponsor. The study employed a combination of qualitative and quantitative methodologies, including collaborative workshops, a dilemma role play game conducted with 191 students, aged 15+, from schools in rural and urban areas, and online discussions with stakeholders. Key findings indicate that financial security, personal interests, work-life balance, and job security are major motivators for students when choosing careers. Furthermore, the study identified practical strategies to increase interest in climate jobs, including the need for well-paid internships and the use of contemporary media for outreach. The insights gained from the study informed policy discussions and educational initiatives aimed at enhancing youth engagement in climate-related careers, particularly in promoting gender diversity within the sector.

3.4 Rooftops Revolution

The Rooftops Revolution case study was implemented from October 2023 until December 2024 in Cyprus. The case study began as a pilot study and was extended to a full case due to the strong interest from the case study sponsor Urban Gorillas, an NGO active in urban regeneration and community engagement in transformations of public spaces. The focus of the case study engaged policy makers, architects, urban planning students and property owners and residents in a participatory process on the topic of greening privately multi-owned rooftops. Insights showed

that addressing key barriers across financial, technical and societal dimensions is essential, including equitable access, economic feasibility, and community engagement. The usefulness of the GREAT methodology was confirmed by a request of a follow-up project by the municipality of South Nicosia, as well as the interest and request of urban design educators to utilise the serious dilemma game within their educational initiative.

4 Data, methods and analysis

4.1 Data overview from case studies

The following tables gives an overview of the collected data from the four case studies. It includes the evaluation instruments that were applied by the GREAT academic partners to collect the data, the nature of the data and its concrete format as well as the main impact areas the data was contributing to.

Table 1: Data collection overview

Case study	Evaluation instruments used	Data description & main aim of the data	Data formats	Impact areas
UNDP Exploratory	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quantitative analysis of collected data Internal working group reflections 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> answers per session and session meta data with language/country info Aimed to test interoperability and reusability of data and formats for Play2Act study 	.csv files exports according to sessions/answers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific impact
UNDP Play2Act	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quantitative analysis of survey engagement Stakeholder consultation meetings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> answers per session and session meta data with language/country info/game studio, etc. Liveops dashboard provides high level overview of responses 	.csv files exports according to sessions/answers MP4 video recordings from online meetings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Societal impact Economic impact
Green Jobs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pre-/post questionnaires Data from game interaction 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Responses to items on changes in collective efficacy, collective action intentions, belief in climate change Reflections on the usefulness of the approach and the 	.csv export of pre-post answers in German for the dataset	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participant impact Societal impact Scientific impact

	<p>(researchers notes & export)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 Policymaker Interview • Debriefing/group reflection • 1 interview with SGI Platform provider² 	<p>future potential of GREAT methodology</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reflections in the process and the overall experience • Interview with SGI Platform provider on economic impact covered both case studies experiences (Green Jobs and Rooftop Revolution) 	<p>.docx in German for the policymaker interview</p> <p>.docx in German on debriefing notes</p> <p>.jpeg Miro board image from group reflection</p> <p>.docx in English for the SGI interview</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Economic impact
Rooftop Revolution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Debriefing • Participant feedback form • Quantitative & qualitative data from game interaction (transcripts & exports) • Focus group • 3 Expert interviews³ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participant’s feedback regarding their participation in the game relating to the DiBL sessions & the Green roof subject • Game interaction transcripts and DiBL exported data offering insights on the benefits, challenges, incentives and fairness of a green roof policy • Expert feedback on the results of the game interaction & usefulness of GREAT methodology 	<p>.csv data set exported from DiBL</p> <p>.docx for all transcripts</p> <p>.pdf insight report for engaged stakeholders</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participant impact • Societal impact • Scientific impact

In addition, reflective sessions in the consortium took place on a regular basis (bi-weekly) in the context of WP4. During these sessions, experiences from the cases were shared and recorded. These collective reflections were also incorporated in the following analysis.

4.2 Data analysis

We collected two basic types of data: qualitative and quantitative; this is partly corresponding to the nature of the game interventions, but there is also both types of data available across all four case studies. As we have multiple data sources in all case studies we speak about data triangulation, which refers to a common research approach in social sciences where multiple methods, data

² Audio recording and transcript shared on a local server of the evaluation WP leader.

³ All interviews were done online via Zoom, videos are stored on a local server of the case study leading partner; anonymized transcripts have been shared with the evaluation team via a shared drive folder.

sources, or perspectives are combined to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the specific research issue.

4.2.1 Quantitative data analysis

Due to the very distinct nature of the two game-based approaches in GREAT, the PlanetPlay platform and the SGI platform game, we also obtained different quantitative datasets from the case studies. In the following we present the different approaches we took in the data analysis respectively.

4.2.1.1 UNDP Exploratory and Play2Act Case Studies

Both UNDP case studies – Exploratory and Play2Act - used comparable methods for data collection and were analysed with a similar approach. The aim of the analysis was to detect connections between players attitudes towards the use of games for climate action and their broader policy preferences, their willingness for taking action, and their sociodemographic characteristics.

Survey responses from the UNDP exploratory case study were assessed using psychometric network analysis (Borsboom et al., 2021), a technique that provides a holistic overview of the interrelations of a given set of variables. In network analysis, variables are called “nodes” and relationships between nodes are called “edges”. These interrelations are partial correlations between all nodes, meaning that the relationship between any two nodes in the network is adjusted for the relationships they have with all other nodes in the network. The results can be presented in a network graph, allowing an overview of clusters or isolated nodes. Moreover, the relevance of specific nodes can be assessed using so-called centrality measures. Main centrality measures we focused on are *strength*, reflecting how strongly a node is connected to others on average; *closeness*, which describes how accessible a node is from other nodes in the network; and *betweenness*, indicating how often a node acts as a bridge between other nodes.

The analysis of the UNDP Play2Act case study required a slightly modified approach due to two key factors: (a) the survey distribution across various game studios led to diverging datasets, and (b) the use of single-choice rather than multiple-choice questions altered the correlation structure, which would have biased the network analysis if conducted in the same manner as in the UNDP exploratory case study. For instance, one game studio excluded demographic data and did not link participants to the PlanetPlay platform, where users could create accounts to stay informed about

climate action. This required segmented analysis of the data. To account for these factors, we analysed the Play2Act case study using bivariate correlation analysis. We used Pearson correlations to account for the binary nature of the variables. All correlations reported in section 5.4 are significant at the $\alpha = 0.05$ level.

4.2.1.2 Green Jobs Case Study

The SGI game implemented in the Green Jobs case study was evaluated using quantitative pre- and post-questionnaires, measured directly before and after the game. The questionnaire included scales on climate change engagement validated in previous research, specifically 1) collective efficacy beliefs related to climate change, 2) collective action intentions related to climate change, and 3) belief in the reality and human cause of climate change. Additionally, we measured participants' perceptions of the discussions during the SGI intervention in the post-questionnaire. All scales were taken from the GREAT Deliverable D5.1 (Koller et al. 2023)⁴. The complete results will be reported in an academic manuscript available at Zenodo in February 2025.

Using Structural Equation Modelling (Kline, 2023), a statistical technique for modelling complex relationships between several variables, we assessed a) pre- and post-differences for our three main measures; and b) to which extent any differences could be explained by participants' perceptions of the discussions.

4.2.2 Qualitative data analysis

Next to the rich quantitative data, the case studies also provided a rich set of qualitative data collected mainly via interviews, focus groups, personal observations and the detailed case study reports. For the qualitative data analysis, we were mainly using a hermeneutic approach to qualitative content analysis, a method that helps us to order and structure manifest and latent content in and across our transcripts and text-based data collections. We are referring mainly to Mayring (2019), who has co-developed the method since the early 1980s in the tradition of objective hermeneutics and grounded theory. At the centre of the analytical process is the

⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12659459>

systematic coding of text material and the focus for this coding was on a qualitative interpretation of the data.

In the coding process, a team of two researchers was assigning categories to the data material. This was done deductively alongside the category system developed on the basis of the logic models, the impact categories and sub-categories, which were presented in Deliverable 5.1 (Koller et al. 2023)⁵. MAXQDA⁶ was used as the qualitative data analysis software.

⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12659459>

⁶ <https://www.maxqda.com/>

5 Mid-term results

Table 2 below gives an overview of the total number of participants involved in each of the four case studies as well as their gender and age distribution.

Table 2. Overview of participants considered in quantitative analysis.

Case study	UNDP Exploratory	UNDP Play2Act	Green Jobs ⁷	Rooftop Revolution
Total Participants	2.113	178.038	191	97
% female	9%	37%	53%	72%
% male	84%	50%	47%	28%
% non-binary		3%	/	/
% prefer not to say	7% ⁸	10%	/	/
Age Range	Under 18 to 16+ years 18 to 35 years is most frequent category	13 to 60+ years 18 to 35 years is most frequent category	15 to 20 years	18 – 75 years 18 to 35 years is most frequent category

In the following we present our interim insights from the four case studies along the four impact areas defined for GREAT: participant impact, scientific impact, economic impact, and societal impact.

⁷ In this case study, participants’ gender was not derived based on self-identification but designated by the researchers to protect participants’ anonymity during data collection.

⁸ The third category for measuring gender was “X”.

5.1 Participant dimension of GREAT

The participant dimension focuses on the impact the GREAT methodology can have on individual actors involved in the activities. This can be mostly players, but also those participating in participatory processes of GREAT, such as data sprints or co-creation sessions, policy makers, and related stakeholders.

Figure 1: Logic model for assessing the participant dimension

In our mid-term evaluation we have found evidence across cases that individuals can be impacted by the GREAT methodology in various ways:

The **Green Jobs Case Study** provides mixed evidence regarding the outcomes of the participant logic model. For the most part, engagement in the DiBL did not significantly impact participants' overall engagement with climate change. However, gains in belief in the reality of climate change were identified after the game and this gain was explained by positive perceptions of the policy discussions during the game.

Overall, most students experienced the policy discussions positively, providing evidence that the DiBL game (SGI Platform) enabled participants to express opinions and participate in policy decisions. The creative and innovative ideas, strategies, and inputs developed during the game further support these outcomes. The quality of discussions during the game was perceived to be high, which positively influenced outcomes, particularly beliefs around climate change.

Notably, we observed considerable variation among the 10 school classes involved. The youngest class, a pre-vocational school group in an urban area composed mostly of male students, reported negative experiences with the policy discussions and exhibited decreased belief in climate change after the game. In contrast, school classes from academic secondary schools in urban areas generally perceived the policy discussions as more positive and reported gains in climate change engagement. However, these variations should be interpreted with caution due to the small sample sizes for each class, which limit the robustness of quantitative results.

To conclude, the findings suggest that many participants positively evaluated their involvement in GREAT, as evidenced by their favourable assessment of the policy discussions. However, this was not the case for all school classes. Finally, the game facilitated personal gains in knowledge and understanding, reflected in improved belief in the reality of climate change. Nevertheless, the findings do not indicate additional personal gains, such as increased awareness or shifts in attitudes. A possible explanation for this finding might be a ceiling effect, as those students who were already interested in the topic before the intervention reported smaller increases.

The **Rooftop Revolution Case Study** provides elements to support the outcomes of the logic model for the participant dimension. Feedback from the DiBL sessions (SGI Platform) showed that the game allowed for the exchange of diverse opinions and constructive disagreements, enhancing realism in discussions.

Overall, participants positively evaluated their participation as they felt that the game sessions allowed for personal learning and perspective-taking. They were able to gain in knowledge on the subject, while being provided a concrete understanding of the subject matter, as well as learning from others' perspectives and attitudes through the green roofs climate change initiative. This two-way knowledge transfer provided a platform where groups not only learned through their experience but were provided a platform to voice their opinions as well as exploring further creative solutions towards urban greening initiatives. These outcomes were documented in post-game

feedback and focus group sessions. The use of real-life examples helped to provide the practical terms, while the perceived clear facilitation and instructions of the sessions made it easy to follow. Therefore, participants saw those opportunities for discussion and clarification which further deepened understanding.

Sessions in Rooftop Revolution incorporated role-playing activities which allowed participants to grasp different perspectives and concerns effectively. However, it must be noted that the approach revealed challenges in ensuring equitable participation due to barriers that participants face (e.g., lack of prior knowledge or scepticism), this varied across the sessions depending on the participants backgrounds. Feedback demonstrated that participants felt the learning aspect was crucial to the influence participants' awareness, resulting in them taking action on climate change initiatives or green roofs in general, with willingness to know more about climate change initiatives being >75%.

Another aspect for the successful engagement of participants is the important role of facilitators: Facilitators played a crucial role in ensuring participation and expression. Participants in rooftop revolution noted that session's facilitator made it both informative and entertaining, explicitly discussing during focus group feedback that the role and engagement with the facilitator is the crucial element in the game. Participants indicated that a less engaging facilitator would result in a less engaging session.

Participants in the Rooftop revolution game were provided a new means of expressing their opinions. By providing a platform for citizens from a range of backgrounds to participate collaboratively (architects, building owners, apartment owners, students, senior citizens, academics, etc) they were able to participate equally. The role-play element of the put 'players' into 'each other's shoes', is a technique not usually seen in urban planning consultation. As noted by expert urban planners at the interview stage, the methodology has the potential to bring new voices to the table who do not currently actively engage in such consultation events.

"Everyone's comes from a different position. It's hard to engage with them all at the same time. The game process helps us remove this hierarchy and put things on an even playing field". Marina Kyriakou, Urban Gorillas NGO.

5.2 Scientific dimension of GREAT

The scientific dimension refers to the scientific outcome of the project, such as a contribution to an ongoing research agenda within the scientific community and to new knowledge on engagement methods as well as the development of new methodological approaches.

Figure 2: Logic model for the scientific dimension

The main scientific impact of the **Rooftop revolution and Green Jobs** is bringing to the table the understanding of how games can be used as a communication and awareness tool/channel. The SGI Platform provides open discussion sessions mixed with targeted quantitative data collection methods within the DiBL experience. In Rooftop revolution, participants openly voiced their opinions past that of green roofs, taking the initiative to suggest a variety of further climate mitigation strategies within the theme of urban greening, as well as making suggestions for how green roofs can be managed and how feasible they could be. In Green Jobs, young people were able to change their perspectives as they could switch roles and act as policymakers themselves. Thus, role-playing emerged as a valuable method for engaging diverse audiences.

As such, the DiBL methodology employed opened new routes of investigation and enquiry to pass to the policy makers. Expert urban planners, including the case study sponsor Urban Gorillas, noted that the methodology could be adapted for various policies and target groups, particularly in environmental and urban planning contexts, as games-based methodologies are not used within the field. Overall, the interdisciplinary nature has the potential for significant impact of the field of participatory urban planning.

Stakeholders face challenges in engaging with each other due to hierarchy and differing positions. Digital games can facilitate social change by educating people in an interactive and efficient manner.”

“The interactive role-playing aspect of Rooftops Reimagined provides diverse perspectives and equal participation.” Byron Ioannou, Head of the Department of Architecture, Frederick University

However, expert planners note that the game requires significant preparation and resources, which may be a barrier for widespread adoption. A potential solution is simplification, making the game more visually attractive could enhance its usability and appeal, particularly for broader public engagement.

The **UNDP Exploratory** case study provides important insights for the new methodological approach related to the reach of new target groups that may otherwise be difficult to engage for scientific purposes. Comparing the survey distribution in-game vs through paid ads supported the potential of games to reach new target groups. In the in-game rollout, engagement rates were substantially higher: 58% of players interacted with the content, versus an insignificant 5% for the paid adverts. Completion rates were similarly higher at 84% for the in-game rollout, compared to 45% for Instagram ads.

A challenge arose from balancing the level of engagement required with meaningful data collection. While games are a very useful mechanism for holding the interest of participants, one concern was that the game-like nature could result in superficial responses due to players focusing more on 'winning' the game rather than reflecting their opinion. Thus, the methods applied must be calibrated with care to avoid the over-gamification trap, and ensure the findings obtained are a fair reflection of public opinion.

An important scientific gain that will contribute to the Open Science practices is the large open dataset the **Play2Act** case study has brought forward. Having reached approx. 900.000 gamers globally leading to approx. 180.000 completed surveys provides a unique dataset. While we can only see first indications of how this data can be used for scientific purposes at the point of writing this deliverable, we can already identify important contributions. One of the options of using the open science data for participatory processes are the public data sprints that are planned for the final year of the project. The mini data sprints that were conducted in the pilot case studies already proved useful for climate-related discussions, aiding the understanding of the climate context within short periods (Watson et al. 2024).

Evidence for the scientific impact is also supported by the academic publications that have already been achieved. At the time of writing this deliverable, a total of **11 publications** have been completed. They are accessible via the Zenodo GREAT community⁹.

5.3 Economic dimension of GREAT

The economic impact of GREAT activities is mostly expected to benefit the commercial partners in the project (SGI and PlanetPlay) and contribute to the business propositions of these partners, while potentially being leveraged by the gaming industry. In the long-term, the learnings from the GREAT project can contribute to the shaping of new green visions for game-based approaches and the games sector overall.

⁹ <https://zenodo.org/communities/101094766/records>

Figure 3: Logic model for economic dimension

For the mid-term insights on the potential economic impact of the GREAT project, we rely on the views of the two commercial partners in the project. Thus, we present the economic impact insights according to the partners' current experiences of how GREAT has already impacted their businesses and the potential it holds for their future vision and goals.

Overall, the collaboration with game studios allowed the project to reach broader audiences, providing insights into new business models. The involvement of studios, including key players in the industry, was confirmed. Commercial partners could improve their portfolio, as evidenced by the development of DiBL 2.0 by SGI and the engagement of new target groups.

Economic midterm impact of GREAT from the perspective of Serious Games Interactive (SGI)

SGI is a Danish company founded in 2006, based in Copenhagen, working in the field of serious games. They have extensive experience with both Danish, European and other international clients within a range of domains and industries. Their extensive experience includes working with different formats, platforms, and technologies. By combining game design, game technology,

instructional design, and psychology, SGI offers serious games, simulations, and training. Currently, SGI has around 14 employees serving a variety of target groups, organisations, and domains spanning companies, NGOs, schools, universities, municipalities and governments. Clients include WHO, Maersk, Amnesty, Novo Nordisk, and the EU Commission to harness the potential of games. SGI's revenue is currently around EUR 1.7 mio. with 57% coming from our domestic market, and 43% from countries in the EU.

Up to now, the most important impact for SGI has been on the developmental side, refining tools and features rather than generating financial or customer-based outcomes. Highly valuable insights have been gained in terms of product innovation. Feedback from users has led to technical refinements, new features, and improved data collection/export processes. Efforts are being made to simplify the game creation process to make it accessible for NGOs and policymakers.

Innovation leading to economic impact in the future relates to the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI). AI is being explored for applications like live facilitation assistance, data analysis, and generating dilemmas. Technical limitations and the risk of generating irrelevant content are current barriers. SGI has identified the potential for AI to enhance user experience and reduce complexity in game design and implementation.

For outreach and exploitation of concrete project outcomes, different versions of the SGI Platform game are currently implemented. E.g. "Green Jobs" and "Green Rooftops" should be distributed beyond the GREAT project, including activities of the Klimafonds in Austria (see societal dimension). Plans are also evolving around the creation of tailored templates and guides, e.g. videos for specific user groups, such as NGOs and policymakers.

A key challenge is making the tool simple enough for users to adopt while retaining its innovative aspects. Practical challenges with regards to economic impact include balancing offering free pilots during the research phase while building a sustainable business model and addressing the balance between innovation and practicality to ensure market adoption.

For a wider penetration of the educational market, current discussions included tailoring the game for various audiences, such as NGOs, schools, and policymakers. Opportunities to explore business models, market strategies, and partnerships for greater outreach are still under exploration.

The tool's scalability relies on simplifying the process and creating resources like facilitator guides and templates.

The conversation highlights ongoing efforts to refine the tool, expand its usability, and explore innovative approaches to engage diverse audiences effectively. The economic potential was also confirmed by stakeholders in the case study, e.g.:

“I think it's one of the most sophisticated methods of consultation taking place in Cyprus and through gaming. You can shift out of the conversation so much more.” Lora Nicolaou Architect/Urban Planner representative of the president of ETEK, on the Cyprus Town Planning Council.

Economic midterm impact of GREAT from the perspective of PlanetPlay (former Playmob)

PlanetPlay is an NPO funded in 2022, with a mission to harness the power of gaming to address environmental challenges, offering sustainable choices that preserve the joy of gaming while protecting our planet. PlanetPlay wants to make it easy for people to make positive change by playing the games they already play and love, without changing how they do it. They empower gamers worldwide to contribute to environmental action through in-game purchases and gameplay with affiliated game studios. Alongside the pioneering eco-conscious games marketplace, it is also a movement designed to inspire, educate, and mobilise players to support our planet and its rich diversity of life. With a small remote core team, they have driven over \$2.2 million in funding for environmental and nature projects in their first year of operation.

The project has given PlanetPlay a deeper understanding of research and processes related to research. This learning has influenced and improved PlanetPlay's processes. As an example, during the UNDP Exploratory case study, Google Ads was used to test visuals and see how people responded to a visual representation of climate change, a positive vs negative image. This learning was used to inform visuals for in-game promo and ads for the case study moving forward. When working through the details of the research cycle with academics, PlanetPlay realized that this was an important factor to record. Thus, the project has given them not just this deeper understanding of the research cycle but helped them underpin the process and methodology with a systematic research approach.

In addition, the Play2Act case study has received considerable awareness and PlanetPlay is recognized as part of the project. As the games industry and policy stakeholders are eager to stay involved, Play2Act is an initiative which can live on beyond the project and contribute to the further success of PlanetPlay.

PlanetPlay is exploring a new product based on the experiences in GREAT. It is similar to a ‘widget’ that can sit in-game permanently and be a survey tool for studios to switch on and off when new surveys go out. This would ease the process of working with games studios, for them in terms of adding new links to games and for PlanetPlay to automate the survey distribution tool broadly with one click. This would enable PlanetPlay to roll out a variety of surveys to players, whereby the data can also benefit games studios and stakeholders beyond gaming, i.e. utilities, government, etc.

With their close relationship with game studios, PlanetPlay sees a lot of innovation potential for games in the GREAT approach. Games can be the next tool to support global democracy especially on the topic of climate change, which impacts everyone on earth. The GREAT project demonstrates their potential, which will be the starting point for groundbreaking changes to how global decisions are made that impact us all.

With the first two case studies, PlanetPlay has also reached new target groups. Before, the PlanetPlay platform was primarily for mobile studios, while the case studies in GREAT enabled them to test new methods for engaging PC and console games using QR codes to launch the survey on a mobile device. As the results were very good, PlanetPlay now has the ability and option to cover the rest of the industry. Other platforms such as Steam and other stores might be addressed in the future, as surveys will continuously roll out in 2025.

New connections and networks have been established via the participation in GREAT for PlanetPlay. The project has also opened up conversations and potential new business with stakeholders, such as games companies, NGOs such as the UN and Waterwise, and also supporting the understanding of the policymaking side. The case study catalysed enhanced collaboration between game studios and policy stakeholders, cultivating a partnership, and fostering socially responsible practices. This partnership further nurtured the development of games and gave policymakers insights into public perspectives about climate policy and more informed decision-making. Connections with partners and their networks as well as the stakeholders who have agreed to participate and have reached out because of hearing about the project have been established.

Speaking at events and dissemination activities has helped to broaden networks, from gaming to academia to policy making. A citizen network of over 35.000 gamers who want to do more after Play2Act, as well as gaining new connections across B2B, the consumer side has been boosted and given PlanetPlay more opportunity to speak directly to citizens on this topic.

Potential impact for games industry in general

In terms of all the results of the project, we currently see that it is more likely and relevant for a games studio to use the data rather than the process. The data obtained from Play2Act has been hugely helpful for game studios in terms of defining green content and brand strategies, enabling games to be more green but aligned to how their audience feel. Games typically don't ask these questions and this was an opportunity to do just that, and be supported by researchers in the GREAT project, to provide more scientific underpinning. PlanetPlay have also been looking at the data broadly for studios, to help them with new product launches which will include green content. Even studios who did not participate in Play2Act, but may do in the future, have asked for data from demographics to help build their green game content. This is very encouraging as it shows the data is valuable to the studios to engage their players deeply, and to do more for the climate action.

For the future adaption by game studios, PlanetPlay is considering to offer survey widgets in-game to make the process more efficient. A game studio would be notified of a new survey, they decide when they make it live, or not, pick a date, and then they are ready. They would need support in the process and uptake of results but this is a role PlanetPlay can facilitate.

5.4 Societal dimension of GREAT

At societal level, we expect the GREAT outcomes to be of considerable value for policy makers, public organisations and NGOs, as we offer insights and a new method to engage with citizens for targeted communication, participation, engagement, and opinion gathering. In addition, we expect that the GREAT toolkit and policy briefs will provide policymakers, NGOs, and campaigning organisations with a new understanding of the potential of games for societal change and transformation

Figure 4: Logic model for societal dimension

The societal insights of **Rooftop Revolution** emphasise the potential to foster a sense of community and an understanding of shared responsibility among participants. Participants highlighted that they did not comprehend the complexity of implementing green initiatives, or the extent of implementing such initiatives which promoted them to be encouraged to think more of the various stakeholders in policy dilemma scenarios. In short, the methodology impacts on the societal level by encouraging participatory problem solving and shared responsibility.

“Bringing the game as a process to discuss big issues like climate change, brings specific solutions. Community engagement as part of the process, is something that is never done in the planning sector.”
 Marina Kyriakou, Urban Gorillas NGO.

“The GREAT methodology employed in ‘Rooftops Reimagined’ brings to the table new voices that would not usually engage in urban planning consultation.” Lora Nicolaou Architect/Urban Planner representative of the president of ETEK, on the Cyprus Town Planning Council.

Political Level:

Policy makers who engaged in the dissemination of rooftop revolution activities were provided with specific solutions and policy insights gained from the sessions. The new municipality of south Nicosia saw clear societal value in the methodology and have encouraged partner Frederick

University within the GREAT project to conduct a further case study on a policy dilemma they are currently facing regarding a waste management policy which will soon come into play.

A further important insight gained was the need to adapt other existing policies in order to enhance green initiatives. For example, in order for a green roof policy to be successfully implemented then a reform in building management policy was viewed as vital important across all participant groups.

Educational Perspective:

Urban Planners identified the potential to use the game as an educational tool for students, particularly in architecture and urban planning. Student groups provided ideas for integrating the game into coursework and exploring practical applications, such as designing green roofs. When presenting the project at the EENVIRO conference, there were requests to use the game as an educational tool or resource. This will also be further explored in the exploitation plan of the project and can also be assigned to the economic impact of the project.

In dissemination activities, students who attended provided feedback and asked the facilitator to come to run the game within their classes where students already had a relationship to promote more in-depth dialogue. Yet, the game requires significant preparation and resources, which may be a barrier for widespread adoption, as noted from expert urban planners' feedback. Simplification and making it more attractive could enhance its usability and appeal, particularly for broader public engagement.

Similarly, in the **Green Jobs** case study the policy stakeholder gathered valuable insights. The project influenced policy makers by leading to concrete policy actions and insights that recognised the value of participation.

“We were aware of some of the motivations for your young people to choose green jobs based on previous studies. However, the whole aspect of rewards and bonus elements was not on our radar. With GREAT we have gained new insights that help us steer our green job campaign.” Chiara Cardelli, Programme Manager, Klimafonds

The game contributed significantly to the current “Klimaschulen” (engl.: climate schools) campaign, which aims to promote “Green Jobs” in schools and provided valuable input for additional upcoming measures, such as “Bildungslabore” (engl.: education labs). This new initiative

focuses on enhancing training and education for Renewable Energy, Mobility Transition, and Energy Transition in schools. For the “Klimaschulen” campaign, particularly its focus on “Green Jobs,” the policy stakeholder gained input on critical areas, such as what motivates young people in their career choices, what measures are most effective in encouraging them to pursue green jobs, and what communication strategies are needed to engage young women and non-binary individuals in the field.

When implementing the “Green Jobs” case study, young people indicated that peers and people already working in “Green Jobs” could be important role models and have therefore an important influence on their career decisions. In contrast, parents have a relatively minor influence, and teachers none at all. This finding was surprising to the policy stakeholder, given prior studies emphasizing parental influence on career choices. Furthermore, young people expressed a desire for tangible incentives to choose green jobs, such as tax benefits, higher incomes, or free access to public transportation, which was also an interesting aspect for the policy stakeholder. Another unexpected insight was the value of creating dedicated spaces in schools to discuss topics like “Gender & Diversity.” Such discussions during the game were found to specifically motivate young women and non-binary individuals to consider and overcome perceived barriers for technically oriented careers. From the policy stakeholder’s perspective, these “spaces” for an open discussion in schools is simple to implement yet often overlooked.

During a final intervention involving schools and the policy stakeholder, feedback from participants highlighted the effectiveness of the “communication box.” This resource, which allows students to engage in activities such as crafting devices to generate electricity or constructing solar installations, received positive feedback. Videos featuring testimonials and additional information also proved beneficial. However, the policy stakeholder acknowledged that these boxes must be accompanied by teacher training to ensure proper implementation. Consequently, training for these resources will be integrated into the teacher education program under the “Bildungslabore”. The program aims to foster collaboration among schools, pedagogical organizations, and scientific institutions. Industry partners and SMEs are welcome, although they are not eligible for funding.

From their interactions with young people, the policy stakeholder recognized that the GREAT dilemma game improved participants’ understanding of “Green Jobs.” As a result, they are considering including the game as a resource on the Klimafonds website for project managers and

partners involved in various programs and initiatives. While discussions are ongoing about making the game openly accessible and available in local languages, its potential to facilitate dialogue between young people and policy stakeholders is clear. By enabling young people to express their opinions through mobile devices and interactive gameplay, the game has provided valuable insights. Participants had the chance to vote for their favourite ideas and measures, offering policy stakeholders additional perspectives on “Green Jobs.”

Game-based approach for participation, communication, and awareness

Discussions with the policy stakeholder highlighted the potential of the GREAT dilemma game for “Green Jobs” as an effective communication tool for stimulating meaningful dialogue in schools. While the SGI Platform game for “Green Jobs” was designed for young people, the game “Green Rooftops” for Cyprus could also be used for an interactive workshop with adults, where participants adopted various roles and perspectives. This flexibility makes the GREAT dilemma game equally valuable for adults. With appropriate adaptations, the GREAT game “Green Rooftops” could also be utilized in a range of policy dialogue events, whether conducted online or in-person, broadening its impact across diverse audiences.

The Austrian policy stakeholder voiced some clear indications of how the SGI Platform game can be included as an educational resource on their educational portal. By adopting and integrating the GREAT dilemma games to the specific contexts, the policy stakeholder is confident that they could support and enhance education, foster dialogue, and inspire greater participation in climate-related initiatives.

The analysis of the **UNDP Exploratory** Case Study revealed several insights for using game-based participation as a tool for understanding public opinion, participation, engagement and ultimately, societal change and transformation (see Figure S1 and S2 provided in the Appendix).

While 2.113 participants completed the survey, their demographic profile was not diverse. The majority, about 84%, identified as male, and most were aged between 18 and 35, with minimal engagement from very young or very old individuals. Additionally, most participants had high formal education and were already at least somewhat concerned about climate change. This suggests that games can reach a great number of people yet focusing on only one game might fail in reaching a representative or diverse sample.

The results also highlight the use of games for understanding public opinions and beliefs about games and climate policy. The majority of participants, 57%, believed that games can contribute to tackling climate issues, while 25% were unsure and 18% thought they could not. Most participants thought that games could help address climate change by raising awareness (70%), educating players on taking action (60%), or raising funds for green projects (66%). Fewer participants, 46%, believed that games could enable public expression on climate issues, and only 12% thought games could not achieve any of these goals. When asked about which climate policy areas games could best cover, participants most often selected Energy (31%) and Nature (29%), with fewer identifying The Economy (29%), Food and Farms (19%), Transport (18%), or Protecting People (16%). These results provide insights into public perceptions of the role of games in addressing climate change and specific policy areas.

We used network analysis to highlight how attitudes towards the use of games for climate action are interrelated and connected to sociodemographic characteristics and broader policy preferences. Key policy preferences in the policy areas Economy (investing in green businesses and jobs), Protecting People (building infrastructure and conserving nature to protect lives and livelihoods), and Food and Farms (using climate-friendly farming techniques) were found to strongly influence other attitudes and beliefs. In contrast, beliefs about what the world should do about climate change, as well as identifying as female, were less influential, though the latter may be due to the small proportion of female-identifying participants in the sample.

Further analysis showed that attitudes about which policy areas games could best address were not associated with specific policy preferences in those areas or with other beliefs about games. Similarly, believing that games can contribute to addressing climate change was not linked to broader policy preferences. However, those who believed in the potential of games to tackle climate change tended to see their role as raising awareness and educating players on taking action. These two strategies were found to be associated with support for the key policies in the areas Economy, Protecting People, and Food and Farms, as outlined above. Thus, those who think games can address climate change are more likely to support raising awareness and educating players but less likely to connect these beliefs to specific policy areas.

In conclusion, while many participants believed in the potential of games for addressing climate change, this belief was more closely tied to informal strategies, such as awareness-raising and

education, rather preferences for government-led policies. If policymakers aim to develop new targets and strategies, they could focus on the policy areas of Economy, Protecting People, and Food and Farms, as attitudes in these areas appear to have a particularly strong influence on other policy preferences. This exploratory case study supports the potential of game-based participation as a tool for societal change and transformation, but its potential is not yet fully realised. While participants saw potential for games to effectively raise awareness and educate on climate action, there is room to connect these insights more directly to formal policymaking and engage a more diverse range of participants. Future applications of game-based participation should focus on diversifying the demographic reach to include underrepresented groups, such as women, younger individuals, and older adults.

Additionally, the UNDP Exploratory case study provides large volumes of data for more policy insight that has still not been fully exploited. Community engagement in the policy process was also highlighted, which provided new ways of involving the public in policy discussions. The games facilitated conversations on big issues like climate change, helping to uncover solutions and bring new voices into traditionally exclusive processes like urban planning.

The **Play2Act** case study revealed further insights into how game-based participation can engage diverse audiences on a global level, promote the discourse around climate change, and providing insights into public beliefs and willingness for climate action (see Figure S3 and S4 provided in the Appendix).

The Play2Act initiative was distributed through 30 different video games, reaching participants in over 180 countries, which highlights the ability of game-based participation to engage a truly global audience. Over 900.000 people visited the survey, with 200.000 answering at least the first question. At the time of analysis (December 2024), 178.038 participants had completed the survey, providing a robust dataset to explore the role of game-based participation in public engagement. This outreach demonstrates the potential of using video games as tools for mass communication, engagement, and data collection on critical societal issues. Compared to the earlier UNDP exploratory case study, this survey attracted a more diverse sample in terms of geography, age, gender, and formal education.

In the overall sample, 50% of participants identified as male, 37% as female, 3% as non-binary, and 10% chose not to indicate their gender. The sample was relatively young, with 42% aged 18 to

35, 28% aged 13 to 17, 16% aged 36 to 59, and just 2% (3,229 participants) aged 60 or older. Additionally, 11% of participants preferred not to disclose their age. Participants were also asked about the age at which they left school, and this data was combined with their age to categorise responses according to ISCED levels (based on Flynn et al., 2021). The results showed that 43% fell into ISCED levels 2 and 3, 38% into ISCED level 4+, and 4% into ISCED level 2. However, 14% of responses could not be classified due to missing information on either age or school-leaving age.

Analysis of the survey responses in the overall sample revealed insights into participants' engagement with climate content in video games. Participants who believed games could help solve climate issues were more likely to see games as tools for raising awareness ($r = .25$), educating players about climate action ($r = .20$), enabling players to express opinions ($r = .15$), and raising funds for green projects ($r = .10$). This finding supports the use of game-based participation as a communication tool for fostering awareness and engagement on climate issues.

Participants who held such beliefs also reported higher levels of engagement with games containing environmental content, whether they played these games occasionally ($r = .23$) or more frequently ($r = .10$). They indicated playing games with a purpose beyond entertainment as main motivation ($r = .18$), while other motivations for playing green games were not relevant. In contrast, participants sceptical about the role of games for climate change also were not motivated to engage with green games ($r = .29$).

The survey also explored participants' feelings about climate change and their motivations to engage with green games. The most frequently reported feeling was hopefulness (28%), followed by feeling informed (21%) and powerless (17%). Other emotions mentioned less often included motivation (11%), scepticism or neutrality (8%), and uncertainty (7%).

Participants' feelings about climate change were accompanied with specific motivations to engage with game-based climate content, albeit with small correlations. Hopeful participants were more likely to engage with green games as a fun way to contribute to environmental causes ($r = .11$). Informed participants valued games as tools for learning about environmental issues ($r = .11$). Motivated participants sought to connect with others interested in climate action through games ($r = .10$).

In contrast, participants feeling sceptical, uncertain, or unchanged demonstrated lower motivation to engage. For example, sceptical participants were less likely to see games as tools for raising awareness ($r = -.10$) or education ($r = -.11$), though they were interested in games with purposes beyond entertainment ($r = .18$).

Participants who felt unchanged about climate change or environmental issues exhibited a lower belief in the potential of video games to address these challenges ($r = .15$). They were also less likely to express any motivation to play green games ($r = .18$) and rejected the idea that video games could contribute to raising awareness ($r = -.10$). This suggests that a lack of emotional engagement may correlate with limited interest in gamified initiatives for environmental causes.

Similarly, participants who felt unsure about their emotions regarding climate change were more likely to believe that video games cannot play a role in addressing climate or environmental issues ($r = .21$). They rejected the notion that games could raise awareness ($r = -.13$) or educate players on climate action ($r = -.11$) and showed no motivation to play green games ($r = .37$). Furthermore, they were more likely to lack knowledge of climate-related agreements or plans ($r = .22$), indicating a potential gap in awareness and engagement that gamified interventions might struggle to bridge without addressing this uncertainty. These findings highlight the potential of using video games to elicit positive emotional engagement and connect with varied audiences, which can be leveraged by policymakers and organisations for promoting societal change.

The survey also explored participants' knowledge of climate agreements and plans. Belief in the role of video games correlated with greater awareness of climate-related agreements and plans ($r = -.18$ for lack of knowledge), like the Paris Climate Change Agreement. Those who have played green games also demonstrated higher awareness of such agreements ($r = -.17$ for occasional players, $r = -.13$ for frequent players). These results suggest that game-based participation can bridge awareness gaps by connecting players to broader environmental and policy initiatives. This supports the use of game-based participation as a tool for fostering informed and engaged citizens.

Analysis of a subsample with sociodemographic data (132,312 participants) and PlanetPlay sign ups revealed additional patterns of responses. In general, attitudes towards the role of video games for climate change were not associated with signing up to the PlanetPlay platform. Male participants were slightly more likely to believe in the potential of video games for addressing climate issues ($r = .11$) and were marginally more likely to sign up for PlanetPlay ($r = .09$). Higher levels of formal

education (i.e., leaving education at age 20 or older) were positively correlated with knowledge of climate agreements, such as the Paris Climate Agreement ($r = .14$). However, age, other levels of formal education, and other gender identities showed no meaningful relationships with attitudes towards video games or PlanetPlay signups.

To conclude, these results position game-based participation as a promising approach for addressing complex societal challenges through innovative and scalable methods. The Play2Act case study demonstrated how video games can be leveraged for gathering data and engaging participants, highlighting their effectiveness as tools for communication, participation, and opinion-gathering on current issues. The survey analysis also provides policymakers, NGOs, and campaign organisations with a deeper understanding of how video games can foster societal transformation, bridging gaps in awareness and motivating public engagement on climate action.

6 Conclusions & Outlook

The mid-term evaluation of the GREAT project highlights the potential of game-based approaches to enhance climate engagement, policy participation, and public discourse. The case studies show that games can act as effective tools for both data collection and public engagement, providing new ways for policymakers, educators, and researchers to reach audiences often underrepresented in traditional climate discussions.

A major strength of the project has been its ability to reach large audiences, especially through the Play2Act case study, which reached over 900.000 participants globally. The range of approaches tested in the case studies offers valuable comparisons: PlanetPlay Platform games effectively reach a broad audience and provide scalable data collection, while dilemma-based role-playing games, such as the SGI Platform games, foster deeper engagement and more detailed discussions on climate issues.

At the same time, the findings reveal challenges that need to be addressed further. One concern is the demographic bias in participation regarding gender and age. Both types of digital game-based studies have mainly involved young participants while older adults are underrepresented. Furthermore, the two UNDP case studies using the PlanetPlay platform involved more male participants than female, whereas participants engaged via the SGI platform were mainly female. As the platforms comprise different forms of engagement and policy input, future strategies may be needed to involve more diverse participant groups for each of the two platforms. In this context, and specifically when considering the age distribution of participants, it should be acknowledged that the project's game-based approaches require digital devices (e.g., smartphones, tablets) for participation, which can contribute to digital exclusion. This might explain the overrepresentation of young participants. Other groups at risk of digital exclusion due to economic status, age or limited access to technology, should be addressed or studied in the future. Another challenge is ensuring the sustainability of game-based interventions beyond the project, which will require additional efforts to develop facilitator training, accessible tools, and partnerships with stakeholders such as NGOs, policymakers, and educators.

The insights gained from these initial experiences lead to the following recommendations in order to maximise the project's impact:

1. Increasing demographic diversity: Outreach should target groups such as women or older adults to ensure more balanced participation.
2. Improving tools and resources: Game interfaces and facilitation guides should be simplified and tailored for different users, including policymakers, NGOs, and educators, to make them easier to adopt and use.
3. Using data for policy impact: The rich datasets from studies like Play2Act can be further analysed to create policy briefs, support public data sprints, and guide academic outputs, linking findings to practical climate solutions.
4. Developing educational and policy guidance: Lessons from Green Jobs and Rooftop Revolution can inform the creation of materials and workshops for use in schools, urban planning, and community engagement.
5. Building partnerships and sustainability: Collaborations with game studios, NGOs, and other organisations should focus on scaling up game-based participation models, including custom versions of dilemma games for specific contexts.

The project's contributions, such as large datasets, innovative methods, and policy insights, are already influencing academic and policy discussions. In the coming months, the team will continue publishing results, presenting findings at conferences, and running workshops to promote the project's impact.

By refining and scaling game-based approaches, the GREAT project is set to leave a lasting legacy in climate engagement and policymaking. The final phase will ensure these methods are practical, widely applicable, and impactful, making a meaningful contribution to both participatory research and digital engagement strategies.

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8 Appendix A: Questions used in UNDP Exploratory Survey

Variable	Question	Answer
q_1	What should the world do about climate change?	Do everything necessary, urgently Act slowly while we learn more about what to do Do nothing
q_2_a_1	To address the climate crisis, how should your country improve transport?	Use more clean electric cars and buses, or bicycles
q_2_a_2		Transport goods on planes, ships, trains and trucks that run on clean energy
q_2_a_3		Improve the design and planning of cities and rural communities
q_2_a_4		None of the above
q_3_a_1	To address the climate crisis, what should your country do about energy?	Use solar, wind and renewable power
q_3_a_2		Waste less energy in homes, buildings and factories
q_3_a_3		Stop burning fuels that pollute
q_3_a_4		None of the above
q_4_a_1	To address the climate crisis, what do you think your country should do about nature?	Keep the ocean and waterways healthy
q_4_a_2		Conserve forests and land
q_4_a_3		Support local communities, indigenous peoples and women that are environmental stewards
q_4_a_4		None of the above
q_5_a_1	To address the climate crisis, what should governments do about farms and food?	Use climate-friendly farming techniques
q_5_a_2		Reduce food waste
q_5_a_3		Promote plant-based diets
q_5_a_4		None of the above

q_6_a_1	To address the climate crisis, what should governments do about the economy?	Invest more money in green businesses and jobs
q_6_a_2		Require more information on how products are made
q_6_a_3		Make companies pay for their pollution
q_6_a_4		None of the above
q_7_a_1	How can your country better protect people from extreme storms, flooding, droughts, forest fires and other climate impacts?	Install more early warning systems for disasters
q_7_a_2		Provide good and affordable insurance
q_7_a_3		Build infrastructure and conserve nature to protect lives and livelihoods
q_7_a_4		None of the above
q_8_ord	Do you think that games can contribute to solving climate change?	Yes
		No
		Don't know
q_9_a_1	In your view, how can games best help tackle climate change?	Raise awareness of climate change
q_9_a_2		Educate players on what we can do to take action
q_9_a_3		Raise money for green projects
q_9_a_4		Enable players to speak up on climate change
q_9_a_5		None of the above
q_10_a_1	What climate topics do you think games can best cover?	Transport
q_10_a_2		Energy
q_10_a_3		Nature
q_10_a_4		Food and farms
q_10_a_5		The economy
q_10_a_6		Protecting people

q_10_a_7		All of the above
q_10_a_8		None of the above
q_11	Age:	Under 18
		18 - 35
		36 - 59
		60+
q_12_F	Gender:	M
Reference category		F
q_12_X		X
q_13	How old were you when you left education?	Under 12
		12 - 16
		17 - 19
		20 or over
		Still in education
		Never went to school
education	Index variable based on q_11 and q_13	ISCED level 0
		ISCED level 1
		ISCED level 2 and 3
		ISCED levels 4+

9 Appendix B: Questions used in Play2Act Survey

Variable	Question	Answer
q_1_a_1	Do you think video games can play a role in solving climate change or environmental issues?	Yes
q_1_a_2		No
q_1_a_3		Not sure
q_2_a_1	How can video games best contribute to fighting climate change and preserving nature?	By raising awareness on climate change and nature
q_2_a_2		By educating players on what to do to take action
q_2_a_3		By raising funds for green projects
q_2_a_4		By enabling players to speak up on environmental issues they care about
q_2_a_5		Games cannot play a role
q_3_a_1	Have you ever played games that include green messages or content about climate change or environmental causes?	Yes, I have played a few times
q_3_a_2		Yes, I have played quite a lot
q_3_a_3		No, I have not
q_3_a_4		Not sure
q_6_a_1	From the following options, what would motivate you or has motivated you the most to play games with green messages or content?	To play games that have a purpose beyond entertainment
q_6_a_2		To learn more about environmental topics
q_6_a_3		To contribute to environmental causes in a fun way
q_6_a_4		To connect with others interested in taking action for the climate or nature
q_6_a_5		To play games with appealing design and visuals
q_6_a_6		None of the above
q_7_a_1	How do you feel about climate change and nature issues?	Skeptical - I am unsure about their importance
q_7_a_2		Powerless - I feel unsure about how I can help
q_7_a_3		Informed – I understand the implications better
q_7_a_4		Hopeful – I realize there are potential solutions

q_7_a_5		Motivated – I feel enabled to take action
q_7_a_6		Unchanged - My views remain the same
q_7_a_7		Not sure
q_8_a_1	Have you heard of any of the following agreements or plans?	Paris Climate Change Agreement?
q_8_a_2		Nationally Determined Contributions, or NDCs?
q_8_a_3		Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework?
q_8_a_4		National Biodiversity Strategies and Action Plans, or NBSAPs?
q_8_a_5		None of the above
planetplay	Indicates whether the participant signed up to PlanetPlay after the survey.	
gender_female	What is your gender?	Female
gender_male		Male
gender_non_binary		Non-binary
gender_not_to_say		Prefer not to say
age_13_17	How old are you?	13 to 17
age_18_35		18 to 35
age_36_59		36 to 59
age_60_over		60 or over
age_not_say		Prefer not to say
education_under_12	How old were you when you left education?	Under 12
education_12_16		12 to 16
education_17_19		17 to 19
education_20_over		20 or over
education_still_education		Still in education
education_never_school		Never went to school
education_not_say		Prefer not to say

10 Appendix C: Questions Used in Green Jobs Survey

This is the English version of the survey. For data collection in this case study, we used a German translation. All items were answered on a scale from from 1 (*strongly disagree*) to 7 (*strongly agree*).

Construct	English	German Version used
Collective Efficacy	I feel confident about the capability of our society to address the climate crisis very well.	Ich bin zuversichtlich, dass wir in Österreich in der Lage sind, die Klimakrise sehr gut zu bewältigen.
	Our society is able to solve the climate crisis if we invest the necessary effort.	Wir in Österreich können die Klimakrise lösen, wenn wir die notwendige Mühe investieren.
	I feel confident that our society will be able to effectively manage unexpected troubles created by the climate crisis.	Ich bin zuversichtlich, dass wir in Österreich in der Lage sein werden, unerwartete Probleme, die durch die Klimakrise entstehen, effektiv zu bewältigen.
	Our society is totally competent to solve issues surrounding the climate crisis.	Wir in Österreich sind absolut kompetent, die Probleme rund um die Klimakrise zu bewältigen.
	Humans can't reduce global warming, even if it is happening. (R)	Die Menschheit kann die globale Erwärmung nicht eindämmen.
	Humans could reduce global warming, but people aren't willing to change	Die Menschheit könnte die globale Erwärmung eindämmen, aber die Leute sind nicht bereit, ihr Verhalten

Construct	English	German Version used
	their behavior, so we're not going to. (R)	zu ändern. Also werden wir es nicht tun.
	Humans can reduce global warming, and we are going to do so successfully.	Die Menschheit kann die globale Erwärmung eindämmen, und wir werden das auch erfolgreich tun.
Belief in Climate Change	I believe that climate change is real.	Ich glaube, dass der Klimawandel real ist.
	The main causes of climate change are human activities.	Die Hauptursachen des Klimawandels sind menschliche Aktivitäten.
Collective Action Intentions	I am willing to participate in a demonstration regarding an environmental policy.	Ich bin bereit, an einer Demonstration für Umweltpolitik teilzunehmen.
	I am willing to organise a demonstration regarding environmental issues.	Ich bin bereit, eine Demonstration zu Umweltthemen zu organisieren.
	I am willing to take part in a strike.	Ich bin bereit, an einem Streik teilzunehmen.
	I am willing to block roads while demonstrating for environmental issues.	Ich bin bereit, Straßen zu blockieren, um für Umweltfragen zu demonstrieren.

Construct	English	German Version used
Perceived Discussion Quality	The opportunities to contribute one's opinion to the conversations were the same for all participants.	Die Möglichkeiten, die eigene Meinung in die Gespräche einzubringen, waren für alle Teilnehmenden gleich.
	In the discussion, only the quality of the argument mattered, not who presented it.	Bei der Diskussion zählte nur die Qualität des Arguments, nicht von wem es vorgebracht wurde.
	A respectful atmosphere in the conversation was important to me in order to introduce my ideas.	Eine respektvolle Gesprächsatmosphäre war mir wichtig, um meine Ideen einzubringen.
	Through the joint discussion, I learned about the perspectives of other participants on the topic.	Durch die gemeinsame Diskussion habe ich die Perspektiven anderer Teilnehmenden auf das Thema kennengelernt.

11 Appendix D: Graphs

Figure S1. Network of variables in the UNDP Exploratory Case Study.

Figure S2. Network of variables in the UNDP Exploratory Case Study. Only relationships $\geq .20$ are displayed.

Figure S3: Correlation matrix of Play2Act complete sample. Correlations of mutually exclusive responses from the same question were removed.

Figure S4: Correlation matrix of Play2Act sub sample. Correlations of mutually exclusive responses from the same question were removed

Network of all variables and edges. n = 2113

Cutoff: 0.3

Maximum: 0.91

Climate Beliefs

- q_1: What should the world do about climate change?

Transport

- q_2_a_1: Use more clean electric cars and buses, or bicycles
- q_2_a_2: Transport goods on planes, ships, trains and trucks that run on clean energy
- q_2_a_3: Improve the design and planning of cities and rural communities

Energy

- q_3_a_1: Use solar, wind and renewable power
- q_3_a_2: Waste less energy in homes, buildings and factories
- q_3_a_3: Stop burning fuels that pollute

Nature

- q_4_a_1: Keep the ocean and waterways healthy
- q_4_a_2: Conserve forests and land
- q_4_a_3: Support local communities, indigenous peoples and women that are environmental stewards

Food

- q_5_a_1: Use climate-friendly farming techniques
- q_5_a_2: Reduce food waste
- q_5_a_3: Promote plant-based diets

Economy

- q_6_a_1: Invest more money in green businesses and jobs
- q_6_a_2: Require more information on how products are made
- q_6_a_3: Make companies pay for their pollution

Protecting People

- q_7_a_1: Install more early warning systems for disasters
- q_7_a_2: Provide good and affordable insurance
- q_7_a_3: Build infrastructure and conserve nature to protect lives and livelihoods

Games and Climate Change

- q_8_ord: Do you think that games can contribute to solving climate change?
- q_9_a_1: How can games tackle climate change: Raise awareness of climate change
- q_9_a_2: How can games tackle climate change: Educate players on what we can do to take action
- q_9_a_3: How can games tackle climate change: Raise money for green projects
- q_9_a_4: How can games tackle climate change: Enable players to speak up on climate change
- q_10_a_1: Games can best cover: Transport
- q_10_a_2: Games can best cover: Energy
- q_10_a_3: Games can best cover: Nature
- q_10_a_4: Games can best cover: Food and Farms
- q_10_a_5: Games can best cover: The economy
- q_10_a_6: Games can best cover: Protecting people

Sociodemographics

- q_11: Age
- q_12_F: Female gender
- q_12_X: No binary gender indicated
- education: Formal education

Network of all variables and edges with a minimum size of 0.20. n = 2113

Minimum: 0.2

Cutoff: 0.3

Maximum: 0.91

Climate Beliefs

- q_1: What should the world do about climate change?

Transport

- q_2_a_1: Use more clean electric cars and buses, or bicycles
- q_2_a_2: Transport goods on planes, ships, trains and trucks that run on clean energy
- q_2_a_3: Improve the design and planning of cities and rural communities

Energy

- q_3_a_1: Use solar, wind and renewable power
- q_3_a_2: Waste less energy in homes, buildings and factories
- q_3_a_3: Stop burning fuels that pollute

Nature

- q_4_a_1: Keep the ocean and waterways healthy
- q_4_a_2: Conserve forests and land
- q_4_a_3: Support local communities, indigenous peoples and women that are environmental stewards

Food

- q_5_a_1: Use climate-friendly farming techniques
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Economy

- q_6_a_1: Invest more money in green businesses and jobs
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Protecting People

- q_7_a_1: Install more early warning systems for disasters
- q_7_a_2: Provide good and affordable insurance
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Games and Climate Change

- q_8_ord: Do you think that games can contribute to solving climate change?
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- q_9_a_3: How can games tackle climate change: Raise money for green projects
- q_9_a_4: How can games tackle climate change: Enable players to speak up on climate change
- q_10_a_1: Games can best cover: Transport
- q_10_a_2: Games can best cover: Energy
- q_10_a_3: Games can best cover: Nature
- q_10_a_4: Games can best cover: Food and Farms
- q_10_a_5: Games can best cover: The economy
- q_10_a_6: Games can best cover: Protecting people

Sociodemographics

- q_11: Age
- q_12_F: Female gender
- q_12_X: No binary gender indicated
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Figure S3: Correlation matrix of Play2Act complete sample. Correlations of mutually exclusive responses from the same question were removed.

